

The effect of entrepreneurial readiness, adversity quotient, and social intelligence on employability students

Nizar Zulmi, Fatwa Tentama

Faculty of Psychology, Universitas Ahmad Dahlan, Yogyakarta, Indonesia

Article Info

Article history:

Received Nov 30, 2022

Revised Oct 27, 2023

Accepted Nov 8, 2023

Keywords:

Adversity quotient

Career identity

Employability

Entrepreneurial readiness

Human social capital

Personal adaptation

Social intelligence

ABSTRACT

Vocational high schools aim to create graduates who are ready to work, but in reality, many graduates are not ready to work at this time. Low employability is the main problem. This study aims to design and test a theoretical model of the effect of entrepreneurial readiness, adversity quotient, and social intelligence on employability in vocational high school students. The population of this study was students of class XII vocational high school "X" in Moyudan, Sleman, which consisted of 209 students. The sample in this study was 68 students selected by cluster random sampling technique. The data collection method used employability scales, entrepreneurial readiness scales, adversity quotient scales, and social intelligence scales. Data were analyzed using the structural equation model (SEM) through the Smart Partial Least Square 3.3.9 program. The results of this study are the formation of a model of the influence of entrepreneurial readiness, adversity quotient, and social intelligence on employability that is appropriate (fit) with empirical data. The adversity quotient has a positive and very significant effect on employability, while entrepreneurship readiness and social intelligence have no impact on employability. This model can be used as a valid reference in developing employability variables.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.

Corresponding Author:

Fatwa Tentama

Faculty of Psychology, Universitas Ahmad Dahlan, Yogyakarta

Kapas Street 9, Umbulharjo, Yogyakarta, Indonesia

Email: fatwa.tentama@psy.uad.ac.id

1. INTRODUCTION

The open unemployment rate has been increasing in recent years. It is recorded that the vocational high school education sector is one of the highest contributors compared to graduates of other educational levels. Currently, most of the unemployment is caused by the low ability of individuals to work [1]. Individuals with low employability tend to experience more difficulties when entering the world of work or achieving the career they expect [2]. To face the pressures of a competitive world of work, individuals must prepare themselves as well as possible [3]. To address this phenomenon, it is necessary to increase the skills of vocational high school students, one of the skills that need to be prepared and developed is employability [4]. Employability is knowledge, skills, understanding, and personality attributes enabling individuals to get jobs and succeed [5]. Employability is a form of active adaptation of individuals to identify and realize career opportunities that can increase individual chances of getting a job [6].

Employability can be the main capital to make it easier for individuals to find work in the future [7]. Developing and improving employability is very important for improving work skills, communication, self-management, and analytical skills [8], [9]. High employability can help individuals identify various alternative career opportunities and appropriate work environments [10], [11], enabling individuals to move

independently to create jobs and implement their potential to the fullest [12]. Employability can affect individual behavior or efforts in looking for work, the quality of the job chosen, and the job search results [13]. Whereas low employability can impact low self-esteem, effort, and willingness to enter the world of work [14], [15]. Low employability also impacts inappropriate decision making, conflict, inappropriate leadership, low metacognitive skills, less effective performance, low social responsibility, and pessimism [16].

Fugate *et al.* [6] divided employability into three interrelated dimensions, namely: i) career identity, a self-image regarding goals, expectations, personality, and values possessed; ii) personal adaptation, willingness, and ability to change behavior, feelings, and thoughts in response to environmental demands. The indicators include confidence in adapting, a tendency to keep learning, openness to receive input, and self-control in various situations; iii) social and human capital, social capital relates to utilizing formal and informal job search networks, while human capital refers to personal variables that can influence individual career progress, such as level of education, work experience, training attended, skills, and knowledge owned.

As a phenomenon of concern in the world of education and work, it is essential to identify factors that can increase employability. Kallas [17] explains that one of the factors that can influence individual employability is individual readiness to create a business or entrepreneurial activity. Entrepreneurial readiness is an individual's cognitive attribute of the ability and willingness to direct behavior in an entrepreneurial context [18]. Entrepreneurial readiness refers to the ability and willingness to carry out entrepreneurial behavior, which is characterized by individual skills, fear of failure, social networks, and perceptions of opportunities [19]. Entrepreneurial readiness is important for entrepreneurs to face business competition dynamics carefully and provide innovative offers [20]. Entrepreneurial readiness will help individuals carry out a business according to the provisions without experiencing difficulties and obstacles with maximum results and in accordance with the specified targets [21]. Entrepreneurial readiness focuses on individual mental abilities and willingness to direct behavior toward entrepreneurial activities [18]. Entrepreneurial readiness can help individuals have the competence to observe and analyze their environment in such a way that they can channel their creative and productive potential that directs them to self-achievement [22]. Entrepreneurial readiness can help individuals have the ability to explore new areas, have confidence in their skills, and be able to anticipate negative things that can cause failure at work [23], [24]. Entrepreneurial readiness depends on mindset (tendency) towards entrepreneurial activities, therefore, individuals with entrepreneurial readiness tend to have a positive mindset towards entrepreneurial activities [25].

Schillo *et al.* [19] developed the concept of entrepreneurial readiness, which consists of four related factors: i) Individual skills, individual belief in skills possessed to effectively implement and regulate the actions needed to produce products. Reflects the perception of the individual's ability to do a particular job. In addition, it is a self-evaluation of personal skills and control in certain situations; ii) Fear of failure, the fear felt by individuals of failure that will be experienced in the process of creating and executing a business. Individuals will try to anticipate negative things that can cause failure in entrepreneurship; iii) Social networks, social resources, which are seen as investments to obtain new resources in the form of relations, business collaboration, and information. Networks that connect groups of people who can create value and facilitate individual action within a social structure. Social networks allow individuals to connect with the right people to increase the value or quality of business; and iv) Perception of opportunities, individuals are able to identify business opportunities that exist around them, interpret these opportunities and interpret them.

Bohlinger *et al.* [26] explained that vocational education can provide a solid basis for developing individual employability depending on several factors. One of them is the adversity quotient [27]. The adversity quotient is the ability to withstand various difficulties and overcome them by using their intelligence and then making it a challenge to solve [28]. The adversity quotient predicts individual success in dealing with difficulties and obstacles in life [29]. Solving and fighting difficulties is very important because individuals will be happy or not depending on how well they can solve and fight the problems they face [30].

The adversity quotient has an important role for individuals to prepare themselves to enter the world of work in the future [31]. The adversity quotient can predict how individuals will behave in difficult situations, predict resilience and persistence, and can also be used to increase the effectiveness of teams, relationships, families, communities, cultures, societies, and organizations [28]. The adversity quotient can make individuals better understand how to react to challenges and difficulties in all aspects of their lives. In fact, the way individuals respond to adversity is a strong indicator of their ability to succeed in many endeavors [32]. The adversity quotient helps individuals adapt as well as possible to various difficulties, stress and make the best solutions for themselves [33]. Adversity quotient makes individuals responsible for the problems they face when they are in trouble, able to control problems, good at finding solutions, and focus on solutions, therefore individuals who successfully implement the adversity quotient will perform optimally in facing the difficulties and challenges that confront each day [34], [35].

Stoltz [28], in his research, explained clearly that there are four core dimensions of adversity quotient: i) Control, the extent to which an individual can positively influence a situation and control the response to that situation. How much control the individual feels over the adverse situation; ii) Origin and ownership, origin related to blame. A fair and accurate level of self-blame is needed to create learning within the individual so they don't repeat the same mistake next time but improve themselves. Ownership how individuals take ownership in adverse situations regardless of the cause. Accountability for the situation motivates them to take appropriate and corrective action to reverse the effects of the adverse situation; iii) Reach, measuring how well an individual can limit the effects of difficulties in his life, namely whether the individual can limit the effects to certain areas where difficulties have arisen or allow the effects of difficulties to creep into other areas of his life; and iv) Resilience, the individual's perception of the difficulties encountered and how long the individual feels these difficulties will last. They believe that every problem will eventually come to an end. No adversity has the same effect forever, there are always opportunities to improve it.

Employability is multidisciplinary, with many influencing factors, one of which is social intelligence [36]. Social intelligence is understanding other people and responding to unexpected social situations [37]. Social intelligence refers to the ability to cooperate and establish social relationships with others, characterized by situational awareness, presence, originality, clarity, and empathy [38]. Social intelligence allows individuals to show confidence in social situations, show genuine interest in co-workers, be assertive and precise in expressing feelings and emotions, adapt, understand, and respond effectively, and have a high level of self-awareness [39]. Social intelligence is the main approach to intelligence in the workplace, the existence of social intelligence can create a collaborative culture in the organization which will produce a positive impact that leads to behavioral innovation [40]. Social intelligence allows individuals to get along with others by involving skills related to all social interactions and acting appropriately in those interactions [41], [42]. Social intelligence helps individuals understand social rules, social life, can accurately read non-verbal cues, be flexible in different social situations, be sensitive in complex situations, and have a personality that makes others feel valued, capable, loved, respected, and understood [43], [38]. Social intelligence combines some familiarity with interaction styles and techniques that can help individuals achieve goals in relating to others [44]. Social intelligence allows individuals to produce adequate behavior to achieve the desired goals [45].

Albrecht [38] in his research suggests that there are five different dimensions of social intelligence, namely: i) Situational awareness, the ability to read situations and interpret people's behavior in certain situations such as tendencies to interact, intentions, and emotional states; ii) Presence, including various images both verbally and non-verbally, body movements, body postures, subtle movements, voice quality and all cues that exist within the individual which become the impression of an assessment between individuals; iii) Authenticity, other people's social radar to catch signals from individual behavior that makes them judge individuals as honest, open, ethical, trustworthy, have good intentions or vice versa; iv) Clarity, the ability of individuals to explain themselves, explain ideas, convey data clearly and accurately, and articulate proposed views and actions, enabling individuals to get others to work with them; and v) Empathy, having feelings for others or "sympathizing" with others. In this connotation, individuals perceive empathy as connectedness with others, which creates the basis for positive interaction and cooperation.

The purpose of this study was to design and test a theoretical model of the effect of entrepreneurial readiness, adversity quotient, and social intelligence on employability in vocational high school students. In addition, it also examines the influence of entrepreneurial readiness, adversity quotient, and social intelligence partially on employability. The novelty of this research is forming an employability model design that jointly involves exogenous variables consisting of entrepreneurial readiness, adversity quotient, and social intelligence. There is no previous research that specifically reveals how to formulate an employability model. It is hoped that with the renewal of this research, factors that influence employability will be found and can become a reference for vocational high school students in overcoming employability problems to face the world of work, especially during the current pandemic.

2. METHOD

The population in this study were students of class XII vocational high school "X" Moyudan, Sleman, totaling 209 students. The research sample was 68 students consisting of 22 students in motorcycle engineering class A, 22 in motorcycle engineering class B, and 24 in computer and network engineering class A, which were determined based on the Slovin formula with an error rate of 10%. The sampling technique used is cluster random sampling. The steps are: i) the researcher determines the number of samples from the entire population using the Slovin formula with an error level of 10%; ii) the researcher counts the number of clusters and the number of students per class to determine the number of clusters used in the study, thus the

number of clusters in the study adjusts to the predetermined number of samples; and iii) the researcher then draws lots of these clusters until the number of 68 students is fulfilled.

There are five clusters in this study, namely: the light vehicle engineering class, the motorcycle engineering class, the computer and network engineering class, the culinary class, and the hospitality class. After a draw was conducted for the majors of light vehicle engineering (A, B, C), motorcycle engineering (A, B), computer and network engineering (A, B), culinary, and hospitality, two classes (40 students) were selected as the trial sample (culinary and hospitality) and three classes (68 students) as research samples (motorcycle engineering A, B, and computer and network engineering A).

The data collection method uses a scale, namely the employability scale, entrepreneurial readiness scale, adversity quotient scale, and social intelligence scale. The scaling model used is the Likert scaling model. Researchers compiled the employability scale by modifying the employability scale from Tentama and Abdillah [46], which refers to the employability dimension according to Fugate *et al.* [6], namely career identity, personal adaptation, and human social capital. The entrepreneurial readiness scale was compiled by researchers, which refers to the entrepreneurship readiness component according to Schillo *et al.* [19], namely, individual skills, fear of failure, social networks, and perceptions of opportunities. The adversity quotient scale was compiled by researchers with reference to the adversity quotient dimensions according to Stoltz [28], namely control, the origin of ownership, range, and resilience. The social intelligence scale was compiled by researchers with reference to the components of social intelligence according to Albrecht [38], namely situational awareness, presence, authenticity, clarity, and empathy.

The collected data was then processed and analyzed using the Microsoft Excel program, statistical package for the social science (SPSS) 28.0, and smart partial least squared (PLS) 3.3.9. Research data was tested using the SPSS program to obtain the item differential index (rit) and reliability coefficient (rtt) scale. The criteria for a good item in this study, namely having an adequate item discriminatory index (rit) above 0.3. Meanwhile, the reliability coefficient (rtt) with Cronbach Alpha criteria is above 0.7. This study uses the corrected item-total correlation (rit) in the item selection process. Inferential analysis was carried out using the structural equation model (SEM) program with the smart partial least squared (PLS) technique. SEM PLS was conducted to determine the effect of entrepreneurial readiness, adversity quotient, and social intelligence variables on employability in vocational high school students. The PLS used in this study is PLS Student, with a maximum sample size of 100 people.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Results

The results of this study are divided into two parts, namely, the results of testing the outer model and the results of testing the inner model. Testing the outer model aims to test the measurement model, and testing the inner model aims to test the structural model. The outer model determines the specification of the relationship between latent constructs and their indicators by assessing the validity and reliability of the model, while the inner model is a structural model used to predict causality or causal relationships between latent variables.

3.1.1. Measurement model test results

Measurement model in PLS 3.3.9. called the outer model. The outer model test aims to specify the relationship between latent variables and their indicators. The outer model analysis includes convergent validity, discriminant validity, composite reliability (CR), and Cronbach alpha (α).

3.1.2. Convergent validits test

Convergent validity can be seen from the loading factor value for each indicator (item) and the average variance extracted (AVE) value. A scale is said to meet convergent validity if the loading factor value for each item is > 0.5 and the AVE value for each variable is > 0.5 [47]. Based on the results of testing the measurement model in Figure 1, it is known that each item meets the requirements for the loading factor and AVE values. The results of the loading factor and AVE value of each variable in this study can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1. The results loading factor and AVE score

Variable	Loading factor	AVE	Remark
Employability (EB)	0.729 - 1.000	0.703	Valid
Entrepreneurial readiness (KB)	0.732 - 0.927	0.602	Valid
Adversity quotient (AQ)	0.703 - 0.933	0.661	Valid
Social intelligence (KS)	0.885 - 1.000	0.684	Valid

Based on Table 1, it is known that the value of the loading factor and the AVE value of each variable has met the requirements > 0.05 . This means that there is a correlation between the indicator score and the construct score, or each indicator can describe the construct. So, it can be concluded that all the variables of this study have met the requirements of convergent validity.

3.1.3. Discriminant validity test

Discriminant validity can be seen by comparing the AVE root values between variables. A scale is said to be valid if the root correlation value of the Average AVE of each variable is higher than the root value of the AVE correlation with other variables [48]. The AVE root value in this study can be seen in Table 2.

Based on Table 2, it is known that the average root value of the AVE correlation is higher than the root value of the AVE correlation with other variables. Each indicator of each latent variable is different from other variables. The combined indicators are not unidimensional. So, it can be concluded that all variables in this study meet the requirements of discriminant validity.

Table 2. AVE root values

Variable	EB	KB	AQ	KS
EB	0.839	0.036	0.616	0.296
KB	0.036	0.776	0.024	0.058
AQ	0.616	0.024	0.813	0.534
KS	0.296	0.058	0.534	0.827

3.1.4. Reliability

Reliability in PLS can be seen from the value of Cronbach alpha and composite reliability. A variable is reliable if it has Cronbach alpha and composite reliability and 0.6 [48]. The value of Cronbach alpha and composite reliability in this study can be seen in Table 3.

Based on Table 3 shows that the composite reliability and Cronbach alpha values for all variables in this study have met the requirements > 0.6 . This means that constructs that are made consistently or accurately measure something that is the object of measurement. So, it can be concluded that all the variables in this study have fulfilled the reliability requirements.

Table 3. Reliability test results

Variable	Composite reliability	Cronbach alpha	Remark
EB	0.892	0.922	Reliable
KB	0.904	0.923	Reliable
AQ	0.913	0.931	Reliable
KS	0.768	0.867	Reliable

3.1.5. Structural model test results

This research also goes through testing the structural model with the inner model, which aims to ensure that the structural model that has been built is robust and accurate. The results of the inner model can be seen in Table 4, and the PLS output results for the inner model in this study can be seen in Figure 1. Figure 1 shows that the model that correlates entrepreneurship readiness, adversity quotient, and social intelligence uses empirical employability data according to (fit).

Table 4. Inner model results

Criteria	Role of thumb	Score	Remark
Determinant coefficient (R^2)	0.75 (strong), 0.50 (moderate), and 0.25 (weak)	0.384	The effect of exogenous variables on endogenous variables is in the moderate category
Predictive relevance (Q^2)	$Q^2 > 0$ (a good predictive relevance model)	0.237	Good predictive relevance
Goodness of fit	0.36 (strong), (0.25) moderate, and 0.10 (weak)	0.504	Strong goodness of fit (GoF)

Figure 1. Output inner model

3.1.6. Hypothesis test

Hypothesis testing is done by examining the value of the *t*-statistic for *Alpha* 5%, namely the *t*-statistic > 1.96, and looking at the probability value, namely the value of *p* < 0.05, which indicates the hypothesis is accepted. Seeing the original sample value (O) is also needed, and if the value is (+), it indicates a positive effect of exogenous variables on endogenous variables. Meanwhile, if the value is (-) indicates a negative effect of exogenous variables on endogenous variables [49]. The results of hypothesis testing in this study can be seen in Table 5.

Based on the results of the hypothesis testing in Table 5, it is known that the results of the first hypothesis test are accepted. Based on the value of $R^2 = 0.384$, $Q^2 = 0.237$, and $GoF = 0.504$, the theoretical model that describes the effect of entrepreneurial readiness, adversity quotient, and social intelligence on employability in Vocational High school students is in accordance with empirical data. Then the results of the second hypothesis test show that the hypothesis is rejected. Based on the *t*-statistic value = 0.676 and the *p*-value = 0.501. The results of the third hypothesis test show that the hypothesis is accepted. Based on the *t*-statistic value = 7.769 and the *p*-value = 0.000 with the original sample value = 0.645, it shows that there is a very significant positive influence between adversity quotient on employability in vocational high school students. And the results of the fourth hypothesis test show that the hypothesis is rejected. This is based on the value of the *t*-statistic = 0.610 and the *p*-value = 0.544.

Table 5. Hypothesis test results

Variable	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	St. deviation (STDEV)	t-statistic	p-values	Remark
Entrepreneurial readiness→employability	-0.055	-0.050	0.081	0.676	0.501	Not significant
Adversity quotient→employability	0.645	0.665	0.038	7.769	0.000	Very significant
Social intelligence→employability	-0.052	-0.042	0.085	0.610	0.544	Not significant

3.2. Discussion

model produced in this study is a novelty, there has been no previous research that is the same as the model produced in this study. The previous research conducted by Hossain *et al.* [49] produced a model in which employability is positively influenced by skills, soft skills, and technical skills, which are mediated by social mobility. The results of research from Chammaa [50] explain that there is a model that describes the influence of learning and experience on employability through self-confidence. Research by Marzec *et al.*

[51] found a model that explains that job variety and the learning value of work are positively related to work performance mediated by employability. Furthermore, Mohamad *et al.* [52] in their research reported employability models that are influenced by initiative development, self-management, and social responsibility.

Based on the results of the analysis, the first hypothesis shows that the R-square (R^2), predictive relevance (Q^2), and goodness of fit (GoF) values meet the expected criteria, so the proposed reflective model can describe the effect of entrepreneurial readiness, adversity quotient, and social intelligence on employability in vocational high school students due to the model (fit) with empirical data. The second hypothesis in this study shows no effect of entrepreneurial readiness on employability in vocational high school students. In contrast to the results research of Kallas [17], which explains that entrepreneurial readiness has a contribution to changes in individual employability. Individuals with high entrepreneurial readiness can be seen from the competencies they have, such as knowledge, skills, and entrepreneurial experience, knowledge and skills are aspects of employability. So, it can be concluded that individuals with poor knowledge and skills will have an impact on entrepreneurial readiness and low employability.

Researchers conducted interviews with several vocational high school students. Based on the results of these interviews, it is known that students have business skills and the ability to see good business opportunities. When there are many business opportunities around them, students are able to use them creatively and innovatively to become a new business, but students need to develop social networks due to the lack of business relationships and collaboration they have.

These problems do not make students despair, they share stories with fellow students, and exchange information and experiences. During running a business, students feel satisfaction because they have their own income from the business they create, but students still lack confidence because of the limited relationships they have to increase the value or quality of the business. The research results of De Clercq *et al.* [53] explain that strong social networks will make individuals more confident in creating new businesses because they have a better position to complement social resources. Furthermore, De Clercq *et al.* [53] added that a higher level of social resources is usually positively correlated with readiness to start a new business.

The research results of Schillo *et al.* [19] explained that the more capable and willing the individual is, the more opportunities will be perceived, and the greater the individual's social network, especially in a business context, the more likely it will be to have a positive view of entrepreneurship. Research by Westlund and Bolton [54] explains that an individual's social network is an important component when making judgments about the feasibility of a business. Other research suggests that social networks can also increase awareness, self-efficacy, reduce the uncertainty surrounding the creation of new ventures, and offer a source of relevant business advice and emotional support [55]–[57]. Therefore, low and high social networks can affect entrepreneurial readiness in individuals.

Based on the results of these interviews, it can be understood that vocational high school students still experience difficulties in building social networks that individuals can use to connect with the right people in developing businesses, so it can be seen that there is entrepreneurial readiness among vocational high school students, but not entrepreneurial readiness that causes students to find it easy to build social networks with relevant people. Based on the things described above, it can be understood that the hypothesis is rejected because the entrepreneurial readiness of students does not affect or increase employability.

The third hypothesis in the study shows that there is a positive influence of the adversity quotient on employability in vocational high school students, which means that the adversity quotient contribution to the employability of vocational high school students is 64.5%. The influence of the adversity quotient on employability supports the results of research conducted by Aprilia and Arfina [58], which states that individuals who have a high adversity quotient have a greater chance of getting a job. The research results of Jasak *et al.* [59] explain that individuals need to prepare themselves to compete in an increasingly competitive world of work, so individuals must have employability with a good enough adversity quotient to be able to compete.

The analysis results also explain each dimension's contribution to the adversity quotient, with the resilience dimension contributing 96.4%, followed by the reach dimension of 90.4%, the control dimension of 86.1%, and finally, the ownership dimension of 79.6%. Resilience is the dimension that contributes the most to the adversity quotient, with a total effect of 96.4%. According to Stoltz [28], individuals with high scores on this dimension view success as something that lasts a long time. Likewise, consider difficulties and their causes as something fleeting and temporary. The difference is that individuals with a low adversity quotient tend to see adversity as a permanent state, whereas individuals with a high adversity quotient view adversity as a temporary condition.

The research results of Singh and Sharma [60] explain that individual reactions to adversity determine whether it will bring them disappointment, sadness, despair, happiness, growth, and success. The adversity quotient, also known as the science of resilience, measures an individual's ability to handle

adversity in life. Individuals who have a high adversity quotient go ahead successfully and continue to improve in their lives because they have the ability to endure considerable adversity. Adversity quotient contributes to career success for individuals who want to increase work productivity and achieve success in the workplace [61]. Several previous studies considered adversity quotient as a single construct when studying the predictive power of factors related to one's career success [62].

The research results of Parvathy and Praseeda [63] explain that individuals with a good adversity quotient will fight against all odds to achieve goals in life. Parvathy and Praseeda [63] added that every individual with an adversity quotient can influence others easily and help others overcome obstacles in life. Mohamed [64], in his research, explained social intelligence influences performance, both extra-role (contextual) performance and intra-role (task) performance. With adversity quotient, individuals can determine patterns that need to be developed in response to adversity. His control over life influences the response developed by the individual.

Research by Verma *et al.* [65] explains that the adversity quotient plays an important role when business owners decide whether individuals can manage and work effectively under pressure and adverse conditions. The adversity quotient is one of the company's considerations in recruiting and selecting workers for organizational progress, and this is because the adversity quotient will show how strong the individual can be against all odds, take advantage of opportunities, and achieve success. Other studies explain that by recruiting or training workers with high adversity quotient, companies can have high quality workers, obtain better business performance, and achieve higher morale [66], [67].

The influence of the adversity quotient on employability in vocational high school students due to the high adversity quotient in students can be described by the ability and perseverance to face challenges in everyday life by sticking to the principles and dreams that are the goal. Able to control problems, good at finding solutions, responsible for difficulties and able to improve the situation whatever the cause, and not easily give up on difficulties and challenges.

The fourth hypothesis in this research indicated no influence of social intelligence on employability in vocational high school students. Contrary to Casner-Lotto and Barrington's [68] study, social intelligence appears consistent in preparing to enter the working world. Moreover, Walker *et al.* [69], in their research, discovered that social intelligence appears as one of the critical factors of employability. Specifically, they consider communication the only most important skill to have when they graduate. Interviews with several students in vocational high school revealed that they could establish good communication with teachers and their peers. As is the case when the teaching and learning process is in the classroom or practical in the lab, but when they undergo field work practice outside the school, students have difficulty establishing effective communication with co-workers.

During the field work practice, students still find it difficult to build bonds with other people due to a lack of insight into communication, such as how to regulate speech, thoughts, and attitudes corresponding to the surrounding environment. This problem occurs because of an imbalance between hard and soft skills in vocational high school students. Most vocational high school learning prioritizes practical classes, making students have sufficient hard skills above the average of other equivalent schools. Still, adequate soft skills development does not accompany this hard skills enhancement. Albrecht's [38] research results explain that worker communication problems can impact the business and affect employee morale, retention, performance, and the worst case, cause transfers, brawls, or layoffs. Albrecht [38] added that communication skills are a significant attribute for effective performance in social and workplace environments.

Gardner's [70] research results describe that social intelligence in organizations will help individuals communicate both verbally and non-verbally and make judgments objectively and systematically in speaking and acting. Research by Rezaei and Khosroshahi [71] reveals that social intelligence and effective communication are prerequisites for successful performance in life, work, and education. Caballero *et al.* [36] explain that social intelligence includes teamwork or collaboration, interpersonal or social skills, adaptability, and communication skills. Additionally, Gudykunst [72] research added that effective communication as part of social intelligence helps individuals achieve the desired personal results. Therefore, high and low communication skills levels can affect individuals' social intelligence.

These interview results reveal that vocational high school students still have difficulty establishing effective communication, especially outside the school environment when doing practical work. Hence, it can be inferred that there is social intelligence in vocational high school students. Still, it is not social intelligence that causes students to feel easy to communicate with people outside the school environment.

4. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the discussion, it shows that simultaneously the exogenous variables of entrepreneurial readiness, adversity quotient, and social intelligence have an effect on the endogenous variable of employability. This means that the theoretical model of the effect of entrepreneurial readiness,

adversity quotient, and social intelligence on employability is in accordance with empirical data. Partially only the adversity quotient exogenous variable has a positive and very significant effect on employability, while entrepreneurial readiness and social intelligence have no effect on employability. This means that separately the influence of the exogenous variables on the endogenous employability variable can only be explained by the exogenous adversity quotient variable. It is hoped that this model can be used as a valid reference in overcoming employability problems in vocational high school students in facing the world of work, especially during the current pandemic. To enrich these findings, it is suggested that further research can use this research as a reference regarding employability, and further researchers can develop or improve the measurement tools in this study so as to be able to describe employability in certain subjects. In addition, future researchers can design other models to find out what factors can affect the employability of vocational high school students. For students to increase employability, they can apply the model to the results of this study, with the dominant variable that increases employability being the adversity quotient of 64.5%. Through adversity quotient dimensions that can form a high adversity quotient to increase employability. Likewise, for the school to understand the importance of the employability of vocational high school students to face an increasingly competitive world of work.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to address gratitude to the Directorate General, Higher Education, Research and Technology, Ministry of Education, Culture, Research, and Technology, for providing research funding in 2022 so that this research can be completed and carried out without any obstacles.

REFERENCES

- [1] P. Ronnås and L. Shamchiyeva, "Employment diagnostic analysis: Maluku, Indonesia," Geneva: International Labour Organization, 2011.
- [2] M. Yorke and P. Knight, "Evidence-informed pedagogy and the enhancement of student employability," *Teach. High. Educ.*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 157–170, Apr. 2007, doi: 10.1080/13562510701191877.
- [3] A. De Vos, S. De Hauw, and B. I. J. M. Van der Heijden, "Competency development and career success: The mediating role of employability," *J. Vocat. Behav.*, vol. 79, no. 2, pp. 438–447, Oct. 2011, doi: 10.1016/j.jvb.2011.05.010.
- [4] C. M. Van Der Heijde and B. I. J. M. Van Der Heijden, "A competence-based and multidimensional operationalization and measurement of employability," *Hum. Resour. Manage.*, vol. 45, no. 3, pp. 449–476, Sep. 2006, doi: 10.1002/hrm.20119.
- [5] M. Yorke and P. T. Knight, *Embedding employability into the curriculum*. The Higher Education Academy, 2006.
- [6] M. Fugate, A. J. Kinicki, and B. E. Ashforth, "Employability: A psycho-social construct, its dimensions, and applications," *J. Vocat. Behav.*, vol. 65, no. 1, pp. 14–38, Aug. 2004, doi: 10.1016/j.jvb.2003.10.005.
- [7] Y.-F. Wang and C.-T. (Simon) Tsai, "Employability of Hospitality Graduates: Student and Industry Perspectives," *J. Hosp. Tour. Educ.*, vol. 26, no. 3, pp. 125–135, Jul. 2014, doi: 10.1080/10963758.2014.935221.
- [8] S. M. Jameson, "A case study of international hospitality students development of employability skills," *Tour. Hosp. Res.*, pp. 57–59, 2008.
- [9] K. Lowden, S. Hall, D. Elliot, and J. Lewin, *Employers perceptions of the employability skills of new graduates*. London, England: University of Glasgow SCORE Centre and Edge Foundation, 2011.
- [10] P. T. Knight and M. Yorke, "Employability through the curriculum," *Tert. Educ. Manag.*, vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 261–276, 2002, doi: 10.1080/13583883.2002.9967084.
- [11] M. Yorke, *Employability in higher education: what it is – what it is not*, vol. 1, The Higher Education Academy, 2005.
- [12] J. Hillage and E. Pollard, "Employability: developing a framework for policy analysis," *Labour Mark. Trends*, vol. 107, no. 85, pp. 83–84, 1999, [Online]. Available: <https://www.education.gov.uk/publications/eOrderingDownload/RB85.pdf>.
- [13] L. Brewe, "Enhancing youth employability: What? Why? and How? Guide to core work skills," pp. 1–51, 2013.
- [14] R. Benabou and J. Tirole, "Self-Confidence and Personal Motivation," *Q. J. Econ.*, vol. 117, no. 3, pp. 871–915, Aug. 2002, doi: 10.1162/003355302760193913.
- [15] G. Giorgi, M. K. Shoss, and J. M. Leon-Perez, "Going beyond workplace stressors: Economic crisis and perceived employability in relation to psychological distress and job dissatisfaction," *Int. J. Stress Manag.*, vol. 22, no. 2, pp. 137–158, May 2015, doi: 10.1037/a0038900.
- [16] D. Jackson and E. Chapman, "Non-technical skill gaps in Australian business graduates," *Educ. + Train.*, vol. 54, no. 2/3, pp. 95–113, Apr. 2012, doi: 10.1108/00400911211210224.
- [17] E. Kallas, "Environment-Readiness Entrepreneurship Intention Model: The Case of Estonians and the Russian-Speaking Minority in Estonia," *SAGE Open*, vol. 9, no. 1, p. 215824401882175, Jan. 2019, doi: 10.1177/2158244018821759.
- [18] V. P. Lau, M. N. Dimitrova, M. A. Shaffer, T. Davidkov, and D. I. Yordanova, "Entrepreneurial Readiness and Firm Growth: An Integrated Etic and Emic Approach," *J. Int. Manag.*, vol. 18, no. 2, pp. 147–159, Jun. 2012, doi: 10.1016/j.intman.2012.02.005.
- [19] R. S. Schillo, A. Persaud, and M. Jin, "Entrepreneurial readiness in the context of national systems of entrepreneurship," *Small Bus. Econ.*, vol. 46, no. 4, pp. 619–637, Apr. 2016, doi: 10.1007/s11187-016-9709-x.
- [20] G. S. Bapat, R. M. Chitnis, and P. S. Subbarao, "The state of 'Innovation' and 'Entrepreneurship' in India-A Post Pandemic Bibliometric Analysis," *J. Posit. Sch. Psychol.*, vol. 6, no. 5, pp. 6820–6826, 2022, [Online]. Available: <https://journalppw.com/index.php/jpsp/article/view/8216/5363>.
- [21] A. Setiawan, "Analysis Of The Effect Of Knowledge On Entrepreneurship Readiness Using Random Forest Classification Machine Learning," *Tech. Soc. Sci. J.*, vol. 23, pp. 134–149, Sep. 2021, doi: 10.47577/tssj.v23i1.4500.
- [22] A. Coduras, J. M. Saiz-Alvarez, and J. Ruiz, "Measuring readiness for entrepreneurship: An information tool proposal," *J. Innov. Knowl.*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 99–108, May 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.jik.2016.02.003.
- [23] D. Macke, and D. Markley, *Readiness for entrepreneurship: Tools for energizing entrepreneurship*, Central for Rural

- Entrepreneurship, 2003.
- [24] S. A. Olugbola, "Exploring entrepreneurial readiness of youth and startup success components: Entrepreneurship training as a moderator," *J. Innov. Knowl.*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 155–171, Sep. 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.jik.2016.12.004.
- [25] T. P. Location and W. Wind-, *Understanding the Entrepreneurial Mind*, vol. 24. New York, NY: Springer New York, 2009.
- [26] C. H. Jørgensen, *Working and Learning in Times of Uncertainty*. Rotterdam: SensePublishers, 2015.
- [27] R. Hogan, T. Chamorro-Premuzic, and R. B. Kaiser, "Employability and Career Success: Bridging the Gap Between Theory and Reality," *Ind. Organ. Psychol.*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 3–16, Mar. 2013, doi: 10.1111/iops.12001.
- [28] P. G. Stoltz, *Adversity Quotient: Turning Obstacles into Opportunities*. US: John Wiley & Sons, 1997.
- [29] E. S. Phoolka and N. Kaur, "Adversity Quotient: A new paradigm to explore," *Int. J. Contemp. Bus. Stud.*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 67–78, 2012. [Online]. Available: www.akpinsight.webs.com.
- [30] R. Pangma, S. Tayraukham, and P. Nuangchale, "Causal Factors Influencing Adversity Quotient of Twelfth Grade and Third-Year Vocational Students," *J. Soc. Sci.*, vol. 5, no. 4, pp. 466–470, Apr. 2009, doi: 10.3844/jssp.2009.466.470.
- [31] M. Hulaikah, I. N. S. Degeng, S. Sulton, and F. D. Murwani, "The Effect of Experiential Learning and Adversity Quotient on Problem Solving Ability," *Int. J. Instr.*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 869–884, Jan. 2020, doi: 10.29333/iji.2020.13156a.
- [32] L. Tigchelaar and K. E. Bekhet, "The relationship of Adversity Quotient and Personal Demographic Profile of Private Business Leaders in Egypt," *Int. J. Sci. Basic Appl. Res. Int. J. Sci. Basic Appl. Res.*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 403–422, 2015, [Online]. Available: <http://gssrr.org/index.php?journal=JournalOfBasicAndApplied>.
- [33] Hema G. and Dr. Sanjay M. Gupta, "Adversity Quotient for Prospective Higher Education," *Int. J. Indian Psychol.*, vol. 2, no. 3, Jun. 2015, doi: 10.25215/0203.080.
- [34] V. B. Nikam and D. M. M. Uplane, "Adversity Quotient and Defense Mechanism of Secondary School Students," *Univers. J. Educ. Res.*, vol. 1, no. 4, pp. 303–308, Dec. 2013, doi: 10.13189/ujer.2013.010405.
- [35] I. A. Hidayati and T. Taufik, "Adversity quotient of outstanding students with limited conditions," *Indig. J. Ilm. Psikol.*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 195–206, Sep. 2020, doi: 10.23917/indigenus.v5i2.10823.
- [36] C. L. Caballero, A. Walker, and M. Fuller-Tyszkiewicz, "The Work Readiness Scale (WRS): Developing a measure to assess work readiness in college graduates," *J. Teach. Learn. Grad. Employab.*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 41–54, Jun. 2011, doi: 10.21153/jtlge2011vol2no1art552.
- [37] D. Golemandy, *Social Intelligence: The New Science of Human Relationships*, vol. 4, no. 2. Bantam Books, 2006.
- [38] K. Albrecht, *Social Intelligence: The New Science of Success*, vol. 53, no. 9. 2005.
- [39] and S. L. C. Joseph, "Social intelligence, a key to success," *IUP J. Soft Ski.*, vol. 4, no. 3, pp. 15–21, 2010.
- [40] M. A. Rahim, "A Structural Equations Model of Leaders' Social Intelligence and Creative Performance," *Creat. Innov. Manag.*, vol. 23, no. 1, pp. 44–56, Mar. 2014, doi: 10.1111/caim.12045.
- [41] D. Silveira, M. Martinussen, and T. I. Dahl, "The Tromsø Social Intelligence Scale, a self-report measure of social intelligence," *Scand. J. Psychol.*, vol. 42, no. 4, pp. 313–319, Sep. 2001, doi: 10.1111/1467-9450.00242.
- [42] R. Brislin, R. Worthley, and B. Macnab, "Cultural Intelligence," *Gr. Organ. Manag.*, vol. 31, no. 1, pp. 40–55, Feb. 2006, doi: 10.1177/1059601105275262.
- [43] D. Fedáková and I. Jeleňová, "Correlates of social and emotional intelligence," *Stud. Psychol. (Bratisl.)*, vol. 46, no. 4, pp. 291–295, 2004.
- [44] M. Mukherjee, P. Law, and K. Baid, "Emotional Intelligence, Social Intelligence, and Creativity in Early Adolescents in an Urban School Sample in Kolkata," *Indian J. Heal. Wellbeing*, vol. 12, no. 3, pp. 367–375, 2021, [Online]. Available: <https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/emotional-intelligence-social-creativity-early/docview/2593671199/se-2?accountid=15133%0Ahttp://mt6qm6wx6p.search.serialssolutions.com/directLink?&atitle=Emotional+Intelligence%2C+Social+Intelligence%2C+and+Crea>.
- [45] K. Björkqvist, "Empathy, social intelligence and aggression in adolescent boys and girls," *Empathy Ment. Illn.*, pp. 76–88, 2007, doi: 10.1017/CBO9780511543753.006.
- [46] F. Tentama and M. H. Abdillah, "Student employability examined from academic achievement and self-concept," *Int. J. Eval. Res. Educ.*, vol. 8, no. 2, p. 243, Jun. 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijere.v8i2.18128.
- [47] M. Hair, J.F. Jr, hult, G.T.M., Ringle, C. and Sarstedt, *A Primer on Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM)*. 2013.
- [48] J. F. Hair, M. Sarstedt, T. M. Pieper, and C. M. Ringle, "The Use of Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling in Strategic Management Research: A Review of Past Practices and Recommendations for Future Applications," *Long Range Plann.*, vol. 45, no. 5–6, pp. 320–340, Oct. 2012, doi: 10.1016/j.lrp.2012.09.008.
- [49] M. M. Hossain, M. Alam, M. Alamgir, and A. Salat, "Factors affecting business graduates' employability—empirical evidence using partial least squares (PLS)," *Educ. + Train.*, vol. 62, no. 3, pp. 292–310, Feb. 2020, doi: 10.1108/ET-12-2018-0258.
- [50] C. Chammaa, "Higher Education and Employability: Building Student's Self-confidence and Efficacy," *Springer Proc. Bus. Econ.*, pp. 47–69, 2017, doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-54419-9_3.
- [51] I. Marzec, A. Austen, A. Frączkiewicz-Wronka, and B. Zaczny, "The impact of job content on employability and job performance in public organizations," *Int. J. Manpow.*, vol. 42, no. 4, pp. 628–643, Jun. 2021, doi: 10.1108/IJM-11-2019-0502.
- [52] M. Mohamad, H. Jamaludin, Z. A. Zawawi, and W. N. W. Hanafi, "Determinants Influencing Employability Skills: Undergraduate Perception," *An Int. J.*, vol. 10, no. 3, p. 568, 2018, [Online]. Available: <https://search.proquest.com/openview/78d03075833f2df0de818017f47b44a0/1?pq-origsite=gscholar&cbl=696409>.
- [53] D. De Clercq, D. S. K. Lim, and C. H. Oh, "Individual-Level Resources and New Business Activity: The Contingent Role of Institutional Context," *Entrep. Theory Pract.*, vol. 37, no. 2, pp. 303–330, Mar. 2013, doi: 10.1111/j.1540-6520.2011.00470.x.
- [54] H. Westlund and R. Bolton, "Local Social Capital and Entrepreneurship," *Small Bus. Econ.*, vol. 21, no. 2, pp. 77–113, 2003, doi: 10.1023/A:1025024009072.
- [55] M. Minniti and C. Nardone, "Being in someone else's shoes: Gender and nascent entrepreneurship," *Small Bus. Econ. J.*, vol. 28(2–3), pp. 223–239, 2007, doi: 0.1007/s11187-006-9017-y.
- [56] P. Davidsson and B. Honig, "The role of social and human capital among nascent entrepreneurs," *J. Bus. Ventur.*, vol. 18, no. 3, pp. 301–331, May 2003, doi: 10.1016/S0883-9026(02)00097-6.
- [57] T. S. Manolova, N. M. Carter, I. M. Manev, and B. S. Gyoshev, "The differential effect of men and women entrepreneurs' human capital and networking on growth expectancies in Bulgaria," *Entrep. Theory Pract.*, vol. 31, no. 3, pp. 407–426, 2007, doi: 10.1111/j.1540-6520.2007.00180.x.
- [58] E. D. Aprilia and D. F. Arfina, "Adversity Quotient and Employability in Fresh Graduate," in *Proceedings of the 1st International Conference on Psychology*, 2019, pp. 82–89, doi: 10.5220/0009437900820089.
- [59] F. Jasak, N. Sugiharsono, and S. Sukidjo, "The Role of Soft Skills and Adversity Quotient on Work Readiness among Students in University," *Din. Pendidik.*, vol. 15, no. 1, pp. 26–39, Jun. 2020, doi: 10.15294/dp.v15i1.23530.

- [60] S. Singh and T. Sharma, "Affect of Adversity Quotient on the Occupational Stress of IT Managers in India," *Procedia Comput. Sci.*, vol. 122, pp. 86–93, 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.procs.2017.11.345.
- [61] Y. Zhao and B. Sang, "The role of emotional quotients and adversity quotients in career success," *Front. Psychol.*, vol. 14, Feb. 2023, doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1128773.
- [62] Urquijo, Extremera, and Azanza, "The Contribution of Emotional Intelligence to Career Success: Beyond Personality Traits," *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health*, vol. 16, no. 23, p. 4809, Nov. 2019, doi: 10.3390/ijerph16234809.
- [63] D. U. Parvathy and P. M., "Relationship between Adversity Quotient and Academic Problems among Student Teachers," *IOSR J. Humanit. Soc. Sci.*, vol. 19, no. 11, pp. 23–26, 2014, doi: 10.9790/0837-191172326.
- [64] E. S. A. Mohamed, "The impact of social intelligence and employees' collective self-efficacy on service provider's performance in the Egyptian governmental hospitals," *Int. J. Disruptive Innov. Gov.*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 58–80, Jan. 2021, doi: 10.1108/IJDIG-07-2020-0003.
- [65] S. Verma, A. Aggarwal, and H. Bansal, "The Relationship between Emotional Intelligence (EQ) and Adversity Quotient (AQ)," *IOSR J. Bus. Manag.*, vol. 19, no. 01, pp. 49–53, Jan. 2017, doi: 10.9790/487X-1901024953.
- [66] J. Kanjanakaroon, "Relationship between Adversity Quotient and Self-empowerment of Students in Schools under the Jurisdiction of the Office of the Basic Education Commission," *Int. J. Learn. Annu. Rev.*, vol. 18, no. 5, pp. 349–360, 2012, doi: 10.18848/1447-9494/CGP/v18i05/47623.
- [67] P.-L. Chin and M.-L. Hung, "Psychological Contract Breach and Turnover Intention: The Moderating Roles of Adversity Quotient and Gender," *Soc. Behav. Personal. an Int. J.*, vol. 41, no. 5, pp. 843–859, Jun. 2013, doi: 10.2224/sbp.2013.41.5.843.
- [68] J. Casner-Lotto and L. Barrington, "Are They Really Ready to Work? Employers' Perspectives on the Basic Knowledge and Applied Skills of New Entrants to the 21st Century US Workforce.," 2006, doi: Are they really ready to work? Employers' perspectives on the basic knowledge and applied skills of new entrants to the 21st century workforce.
- [69] A. Walker, M. Yong, L. Pang, C. Fullarton, B. Costa, and A. M. T. Dunning, "Work readiness of graduate health professionals," *Nurse Educ. Today*, vol. 33, no. 2, pp. 116–122, Feb. 2013, doi: 10.1016/j.nedt.2012.01.007.
- [70] H. Gardner, "Multiple intelligences: the theory in practice," *Choice Rev. Online*, vol. 31, no. 02, pp. 31-1214-31-1214, 1993, doi: 10.5860/choice.31-1214.
- [71] A. Rezaei and J. Bahadori Khosroshahi, "Optimism, Social Intelligence and Positive Affect as Predictors of University Students' Life Satisfaction," *Eur. J. Ment. Heal.*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 150–162, 2018, doi: 10.5708/EJMh.13.2018.2.3.
- [72] W. B. Gudykunst, "Intercultural Communication Competence," in *Cross-Cultural and Intercultural Communication*, London: Sage Publications, 2003.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Nizar Zulmi is a graduate of the master of psychology at Universitas Ahmad Dahlan, Yogyakarta. Nizar Zulmi holds a bachelor's degree in the Psychology Study Program, Faculty of Psychology, Universitas Ahmad Dahlan, Yogyakarta, with a concentration in industrial and organizational psychology. Currently, the focus of his research is on the theme of student work readiness. He can be contacted at email: nizarzulme@gmail.com.

Fatwa Tentama is a lecturer at the Faculty of Psychology, Universitas Ahmad Dahlan, Yogyakarta. Fatwa Tentama obtained a master's degree in psychology from Universitas Mercu Buana, Yogyakarta, and a doctorate in psychology from Universitas Persada Indonesia, Jakarta. His research focuses on work attitudes and behavior, including Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB), employability, work readiness, entrepreneurship readiness, entrepreneurial intentions, and contextual performance. He can be contacted email: fatwa.tentama@psy.uad.ac.id.